

Developing an image of *Apis mellifica*

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Generating an entire "image" of a remedy from seemingly separate fragments is not easy. Through experience I have come to understand a little more about the remedy *Apis*. It is not a rare remedy, yet I believe not too well understood. Here are a couple of cases to highlight some essential features. With each case we see the *materia medica* begins to come alive and an image gradually evolves.

Case 1

Mrs. L., aged 23 years, unmarried with 3 children under 4 years of age, living with her boyfriend (children's father). Presented on 31.1.1991 with a palmar dermatitis, especially worse since last few weeks, aggravated from washing the children's nappies. The bilateral vesicular eruptions (< right side) extended proximally to the elbows and caused intense itching. The itching was worse at night in bed, and relieved by application of cool wet towel. She also complained of extreme lassitude.

Through the consultation, this patient was very talkative, I could only sit back and observe. There was no chance for interruption - this forced me to observe, I had no choice (one really does learn from patients). Loquacity was marked, and she was very excitable, lively, laughing.

She started telling me of her situation in which she lived in a small apartment with the children to mind all day, a "madhouse", as she related. They had no yard to play in, where she could leave them safely and carry on her housework in peace, and she found it difficult to keep them out of mischief in the apartment. The place "was a mess", and she was so tired - very tired, yet she would laugh excessively and inappropriately as she spoke. When questioned on libido, her face flushed with embarrassment when telling how she was too tired for sex when her boyfriend came home at night.

She also told how they had been looking for a house to buy, but then the market took a downward turn and their apartment value fell too much for them to move. Her parents were Catholic, and they strongly disapproved of her unmarried relationship, and her boyfriend's mother was not Catho-

lic and "hated" Catholics. It seemed that her situation was very stressful.

Yet, through all this, I found it difficult to grasp the real tragedy, to empathise with her situation. I asked myself through the consultation, why I didn't "feel" for her; I realised that her words, the situations she described, and her behaviour, were seemingly disconnected.

Her speech and actions were lively, excitable, loquacious. Whenever she told of another hardship, she broke out into laughter, the more she spoke of these things, the more she seemed to laugh, and loud laughter, uncontrolled. Her overall mood seemed cheerful, not sad, as I would have expected from the gravity of her situation.

I found this most peculiar aspect of the case. I used the following *rubrics* to prescribe:

- Mirth, simulates hilarity while he feels wretched (RG., p.52).
- Laughing, misfortune at (RG., p.9).

These two *rubrics* pointed me to *Apis*. In Hering's Guiding Symptoms I found the following symptoms:

- Acts foolishly or with a good deal of levity.
- Busy, frivolous, disposed to laugh, excessively cheerful.
- Exaggerated merriment.
- Eccentric cheerfulness.

And from T.F. Allen's Encyclopaedia we read the following:

- Laughs at every misfortune.
- He laughed at the greatest misfortune, as he would at a comedy.

- Inclination to change his occupation; will not keep steadily at anything.

Of course *Apis* also covered the "excited state" loquacity, the aggravation from heat (of bed) and amelioration from the cool, wet application (*Apis* is > by cool and cool bathing). It even covers the general prostration that this patient described.

I prescribed *Apis* 0/1 b.d. and after an initial aggravation, she reported that her skin had cleared a few weeks later.

Case 2

Mrs. P.O., aged 40 yrs., a stage singer/entertainer, first presented on 5th July 1991 with a 15 year history of recurrent cold/influenza always associated with laryngitis.

But the most disturbing complaint was what she termed an "allergy" to make-up and cigarette smoke which caused a marked redness and puffiness about the eyes, with a feeling of "tightness" of the skin. Especially cigarette smoke would produce sharp, stinging-burning pain of the eyes, which forced her to close her eyes for some relief (also, the coldness of her fingers over her orbits somewhat relieved). If she opened her eyes to the smoke, there would follow profuse lachrimation - "gushing" of tears as she called it. The eyes were very red and injected. Symptoms were relieved by cold application. All this and she was an entertainer, singing and dancing on stage most nights of the week, in an atmosphere filled with cigarette smoke. The condition was so prevalent, that she incorporated the lachrimation into her routine, using the tears as part of the show.

She told me of her unfounded concern that her husband (a priest) might leave her sometime in the future. Also, she said she had a fear of her children dying (she had two children), and a strong fear of being raped.

She also described, somewhat reservedly, that she was having sexual difficulty with her husband. She somehow felt uncomfortable about sex. She wasn't sure why, but sex had been a growing concern for her, and their relationship was suffering.

When I questioned her in this area, she told me she becomes very embarrassed if anyone approaches her in a sexual manner, as happens often in her line of work. Even a slight flirtation will make her flush, and she just won't know what to do, she feels awfully uncomfortable.

I found this point very unusual. Here was a 40 year old woman, singing and dancing on stage in a skimpy, tightly-fitting cabaret type garment, who had been doing this sort of work for many years, and still, she found it most embarrassing to receive the slightest sexual gesture. This was a sexual prudishness, a morbid sexual propriety. A childishness in her sexual development. Normally, one would expect to develop a tolerance to a repetitive stimulus, but in her case, she was unable to adapt to this situation, even after all these years.

Objectively, this patient was very hurried. She spoke very rapidly, excitedly. Quick in actions and in speech. All I had to do was sit back and she did the rest. She just talked and talked, but not in a flowing way, but her speech was rather like her motions, excited, hurried, erratic. Intensely energetic, yet a pleasant type, not aggressive nor angry at all, rather bright, vivacious, lively.

This point, together with the rest of her behaviour, gave me the impression of a child, an excitable, hurried, talkative girl, who had not developed a mature sexual attitude.

This lively childishness, the loquacity and hurry, coupled with the modalities and sensations of the eye symptoms led me to consider Apis. At this point, I recalled the noticeable embarrassment of my earlier Apis case, (case 1 above) when she was questioned on sexual matters, and this in a very debilitated woman with 3 children! This impression of sexual prudishness was strikingly similar in both cases.

I prescribed Apis 0/1, one dose every morning (o.m.). This case was particularly enlightening. Over the next few months, I witnessed, and the patient described, an amazing change in herself.

24.7.1991 No snuffles or colds. No "allergy" eye symptoms, even during performances. RX: Apis 0/1 o.m. to continue.

16.8. Unusually strong sweets cravings. Last menses unusually early (3 week cycle). RX: Apis 0/3 o.m (I had no 0/2)

Sept. No allergy symptoms. Having many sore throats, but they don't last, with swollen glands. But feels generally well. RX: Sac. Lac. (my colleague made this

prescription in my absence from clinic)

16.10.1 Having lots of voice problems - husky voice. Very low self esteem - feeling "very depressed inside" and "looking for negative things to justify her feelings". She said it reminded her of her depressed periods during her twenties. Feels no self esteem. Doesn't like herself, feels that friends don't like her and husband doesn't love her. Life is horrible. Rx: Sac. Lac.

This was a return of old symptoms, and we needed to wait without medication until things settled. The patient went through a difficult period over the next few weeks, but I explained that it would be relatively short-lived and kept her on Sac. Lac.

27.11.1 All symptoms better. Rx: Sac. Lac.

23.12. Feeling really well. Thinking about a change of occupation. Also, is enjoying a good relationship with her husband, feels less inhibited about sex. Even at work, is not so bothered or embarrassed by flirtatious men. She volunteered that she felt she had really "matured" in the last 3 weeks.

At this point I was amazed. The patient had actually stated that she had "matured", and she didn't even know anything about her remedy state, nor about homœopathy. I stopped the medication and explained that we had best wait to see if she could "go it alone" now. The basic Apis state of a mirthful, childishness was removed. This precluded me from prescribing Apis again. I could only wait and see if the "state" would return.

15.1.1992 Feeling well most of the time, but has realised that she won't become a great "star" on stage and feels sad, but she is coming to terms with it. Says it's not the intense depression she had experienced previously. Menses have returned to normal (28 day cycle). No medication given.

The last I saw her was in March 1992, and she felt very well, with no return of "allergy" symptoms.

Some essential features

These two cases have together helped to shape my understanding of Apis. The first, relatively intense case where the patient was laughing uncontrollably at her unfortunate situation, and the latter, less intense yet strongly characteristic case, wherein the patient seemed cheerful, chirpy, and one would never have guessed that she was depressed (as she put it she was depressed "inside"), acting as if she were well

to the casual observer.

Thus it seems that the primary action of this remedy, the peculiarity of its effect in the proving, is to produce a state of cheerful levity, from a mild mirthful restlessness up to a fruitless, frenzied, uncontrolled activity. The greater the intensity of the Apis state, then the more exaggerated will be this state. The stupor, the debility, and even loss of consciousness as Hering describes, are all to be expected after such intense frenzied delirium - these are an expected (secondary) response of a normal organism to such a primary reaction.

Now, if the Apis dis-ease is less intense, then the reaction will be more of simple mirth and frivolity, rather than of the extreme busy, delirious frenzy. Nevertheless, from this case, it became clear to me, that the characteristic (primary) effect of Apis is one of levity, hilarity, excitability, mirth, and when a person behaves in this manner inappropriately to their situation, then this marks the Apis dis-ease.

We can perhaps also understand the following symptoms in the repertory:

- Delirium, well, declares she is (RG., p.17).
- Delusion, well, thinks he is (RG., p.28).
- Well, says he is when very sick (RG., p.76).

The patient suffering Apis disease, may "tell" us they are well not only verbally, but even physically, through their gestures, motions, behaviour, etc. We can understand that if a patient behaves as if they are well, then they are really telling us that they are well through the use of body language.

I would also like to emphasise this sexual "prudishness" which seemed to be present in both cases. This excessive propriety (morbidly proper) response to sexual matters, was not only particularly marked in the second case but it was markedly reduced following administration of Apis.

Finally, of interest was the patients concern for her children's safety (she said she feared them dying), which is interesting when we note the following symptom in Hering's Guiding Symptoms:

- Shrill screaming "oh my baby"

I'm not yet aware of the specific significance of this particular anxiety in Apis, especially considering that they have so many other fears and anxieties as detailed in the works of Allen and Hering. ☒

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